

WAYS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE FOR PASSIVE LEARNERS

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Abstract. *As the demand for learning English is increasing year by year, everyone should be fluent in English. However, there are also passive students; we will discuss in this article how to increase their interest in language.*

Keywords: *ESL classroom, passive learning, active learning, sluggish students, motivation, incentive tools.*

СПОСОБЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ ПАССИВНЫХ УЧЕНИКОВ

Аннотация. *Поскольку спрос на изучение английского языка растет с каждым годом, каждый должен свободно владеть английским языком. Однако есть и пассивные студенты; в этой статье мы обсудим, как повысить их интерес к языку.*

Ключевые слова: *класс ESL, пассивное обучение, активное обучение, вялые ученики, мотивация, инструменты поощрения.*

INTRODUCTION

Almost all students in Uzbekistan are fluent in English. Nevertheless, there are enough students, who are sluggish and sometimes they are not interested in the language. Most students of this type study only to collect points, but outside of class, they do not do any additional work related to language. How does transform passive learning into active learning in Uzbekistan ESL classroom?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Definitions of words

Active learning - It is proposed that strategies promoting active learning be defined as instructional activities involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing (Liu, 2001, p. 215).

Passive learning- Passive learning is that students are assumed to enter the course with minds like empty vessels or sponges to be filled with knowledge (Dean, 2001, p. 424).

ESL. Abbreviation for the term English as a Second Language.

The problem

One of the main reasons for the decline in interest in language learning is the lack of an English atmosphere in the room, the lack of pictures depicting American and British countries, the lack of various posters and the lack of English books in some classrooms. A student who cannot feel the atmosphere of English language definitely lose interest in the language. The most cases teachers are the main reasons to lose interests of their students to learn English language, and they are not able to convey their knowledge skillfully, the students will start to slow down. However, I will try to solve the situation with my own ideas.

RESULTS

Motivation

The reason is that teachers have to have their own teaching skills. He has to take the lesson with great energy; they have to work hard on himself. Teachers always have to be in a good mood. They should use interesting events related to the lesson and release funny videos or movies while the students are slowing down. Must use pictorial materials. Teachers are required to give a little praise when they say one or two words in English; teachers should motivate them through their words. They must know how to use body language skillfully, in a word, a teacher must teach something to students with great energy. Praising students even a bit, it can help to inspire sluggish students and their interest in learning language continues to grow.

Incentive tools

Teachers are required to encourage their students and pupils frequently. Incentives also motivate sluggish or passive learners to learn a language. Incentives can be different:

- Encouragement with certificates and diplomas for active participation;
- Encourage younger learners through decorative shapes made of paper (stars, rectangles)
- Praising through words by teachers, head of school, university, lyceum, etc.

DISCUSSION

Besides, I also have a suggestion that if programmers developed an app like this, there would be grammar exercises on all topics; rising from easy to difficult, and eventually at the end there would be a larger amount of money for active students on this app, which would also be an incentive. Such a thing would be more convenient for university students and would be a great motivator in language learning.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above, I should emphasize that every language teacher must work hard, and have a good relationship with children, and they must be patient in every lesson. In addition, English language classrooms must be adapted to English atmosphere. Moreover, everyone has to learn English to the best of their ability, and English leads to many successes.

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